

ASPIRATSION SINDROMDAN NOBUD BO'LGAN CHAQALOQLAR BUYRAGINING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARI

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Ishning maqsadi tug'ruqdan keyingi erta hamda kechki neonatal davrda aspiratsion sindromdan vafot etgan chaqaloqlar buyragining postnatal ontogenezdagi rivojlanishining o'ziga xos morfologik o'zgarishlarini kuzatish.

Tadqiqot ob'ekti va predmeti. Respublika patologik anatomiya markazida 2020-2023 yillardagi tug'ruqdan keyingi neonatal davrda jami 48 nafar neonatal davrning erta (0-7 kunlik) davrida nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlar va nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlarning buyrak to'qimasi materiallari olingan.

Olingan natijalar. 7 kungacha bo'lgan davrda aspiratsion sindrom bilan kasallangan chaqaloqlar buyragi gipoksiya sababli, epitelial hujayralar nekrozi odatda arang seziladigan bo'ladi va bazal membranalarning qiyinchilik bilan aniqlanadi. Kanalchalarning distal qismi va yig'uvchi naychalarda oqsil silindrlarni bo'lishi aspiratsion sindromdan dalolat beradi. Nekrozga uchragan va ko'chib tushgan hujayralar kanalchalarning pastki bo'limlariga o'tib boradi va silindrlarni hosil qilganligini kuzatdik. Zararlangan membrana atrofida limfositlar, makrofaglar to'planib qolganligini kuzatish mumkin bo'ladi.

Xulosa: Buyrak to'qimasining mikroskopik tekshiruvlari neonatal davrda aspiratsion sindrom tashxisi bilan kasallanib nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlar avtopsiyasida ajratib olingan buyrak to'qimasini morfologik o'zgarishlarini o'rganishimiz shuni ko'rsatadi. Buyrakda qon aylanishi susaygan paytda ya'ni kislorod yaxshi yetib bormagan vaqtda boshlanadigan nekrotik o'zgarish ishemik kanalchalar nekrozi deb yuritiladi. Bunday holatda kanalchalarning proksimal qismi va Genle qovuzlog'ining pastga tushib boruvchi qismi zararlanganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin bo'ladi. Kanalchalar nekrozga uchrashi bilan o'tkir buyrak yetishmovchiligi boshlanganligidan dalolat beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: chaqaloq, neonatal davr, o'tkir buyrak yetishmovchiligi, gipoksiya, Ishemik nekroz, avtopsiya

Mavzunihg dolzarbliigi: Tug'ruqdan keyingi aspiratsiya sindromi neonatologiyada hali ham dolzarb tadqiqot mavzularidan biri bo'lib qolmoqda, klinik ahamiyatiga qaramay ko'pincha, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda va chaqaloqlarda tug'ruqdan keyingi aspiratsiyaga hali ham kamroq e'tibor qaratilganligi kuzatilmoqda. Neonatal davr shartli ravishda ikkita davrni o'z ichiga oladi. Bular erta neonatal davr bunda chaqaloq tug'ilganidan 0-7 kungacha bo'lgan vaqtni o'z ichiga oladi. Ikkinchi kechki neonatal davr 8-28 kungacha bo'lgan muddatni o'z ichiga oladi. Neonatal davrda aksariyat ichki a'zolarning rivojlanishi xar qanday ta'sirlovchi omillarga javoban tizimli javob reaksiyasi ko'rinishida namoyon bo'ladi. Erta neonatal davrda chaqaloqlarda yuzaga keladigan aspiratsion sindromda ichki a'zolardan asosan parenximatoz a'zolarning gipoksiyasi kuzatiladi. Quyidagi tadqiqotimizda ushbu patologik o'zgarishlar buyrak to'qimasining postnatal ontogenezida quyidagi morfologik o'zgarishlar bilan rivojlanadi. Ya'ni yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq buyragi nisbatan katta va yumaloq shaklda bo'ladi. U bo'laklardan iborat bo'lib, po'stloq qavati yaxshi rivojlanmaganligi uchun yuzasi g'adir-budur bo'ladi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq buyragi o'rtacha uzunligi 4.2 sm, kengligi uchlari sohasida 2.2 sm, darvoza sohasida 1.5 sm, og'irligi esa 12 g. Chap buyrak o'ngiga nisbatan katta. Chaqaloq buyragining po'stloq moddasini qalinligi o'rtacha 2 mm bo'ladi, mag'iz moddasiniki 8 mm bo'lib ularning bir-biriga nisbati 1:4 bo'ladi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq buyragining yuqori uchi XII ko'krak umurtqasining yuqori qirrasida joylashadi. Pastki uchi esa IV bel umurtqasining pastki qirrasida joylashadi. XII qovurg'a chap buyrakning yuqorigi uchini kesib o'tsa, o'ng buyrakning yuqorigi uchi XII qovurg'aning pastki qirrasiga to'g'ri keladi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq buyragi uch qavat g'ilof bilan o'ralgan. Buyrak fassiyasi qorinparda orqa fassiyasini yupqa varag'idan iborat. Buyrakning yog' pardasi yo'q. Buyrakning fibroz g'ilofi yupqa biriktiruvchi to'qimadan iborat bo'lib buyrak parenximasiga yopishib turadi va oson ajraladi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqning buyrak jomi keng, ampula shaklida bo'lib, ko'pincha buyrak tashqarisida joylashadi. Buyrak kosachalari homila hayotining oxirida paydo bo'ladi.

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davrning erta (0-7 kunlik) davrida nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlar va nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlarning buyrak to'qimasi materiallari olingan.

Olingan natijalar. Buyrak to'qimasining mikroskopik tekshiruvlari neonatal davrda aspiratsion sindrom tashxisi bilan kasallanib nobud bo'lgan chaqaloqlar avtopsiyasida ajratib olingan buyrak to'qimasini morfologik o'zgarishlarini o'rganishimiz shuni ko'rsatadi. Buyrakda qon aylanishi susaygan paytda ya'ni kislorod yaxshi yetib bormagan vaqtda boshlanadigan nekrotik o'zgarish ishemik kanalchalar nekrozi deb yuritiladi. Bunday holatda kanalchalarning proksimal qismi va Genle qovuzlog'ining pastga tushib boruvchi qismi zararlanganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin bo'ladi. Kanalchalar nekrozga uchrashi bilan o'tkir buyrak yetishmovchiligi boshlanganligidan dalolat beradi. Bunga asosan kanalchalarning zararlanishi preglomerular arteriolalarning tortishib, torayib qolishiga olib kelishi kuzatilishi mumkin. Bu esa ko'ptokchalardagi filtrlash tezligi pasayishiga olib kelishini kuzatish mumkin. Ishemik nekrozga uchragan buyrak to'qimasini mikroskop bilan tekshirib ko'rilganda kanalchalar qisqa segmentlarining zararlanganligi topildi. Epitelial hujayralar nekrozi odatda arang seziladigan bo'ladi va bazal membranalarning qiyinchilik bilan aniqlanadi. Kanalchalarning distal qismi va yig'uvchi naychalarda oqsil silindrlarni bo'lishi aspiratsion sindromdan dalolat beradi. Nekrozga uchragan va ko'chib tushgan hujayralar kanalchalarning pastki bo'limlariga o'tib boradi va silindrlarni hosil qilganligini kuzatdik. Zararlangan membrana atrofida limfositlar, makrofaglar to'planib qolganligini kuzatish mumkin bo'ladi.

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